

Assessing the effect of a partly unobserved, exogenous, binary time-dependent covariate on survival probabilities using generalised pseudo-values

Ulrike Pötschger^{1,2}, Harald Heinzl², Maria Grazia Valsecchi³, Martina Mittlböck^{2*}

-APPENDIX-

Section A: Properties of the 1→2 pseudo-value

Consider a value z , $0 \leq z \leq t^{search}$, and let $\hat{S}(t^*|T \geq z)$ denote the survival propability at t^* estimated by Kaplan-Meier based on all r patients still at risk at z . The common pseudo-value [1] for the k -th patient, $k = 1 \dots r$, is now defined as

$$\hat{U}_k = r\hat{S}(t^*|T \geq z) - (r-1)\hat{S}^{-k}(t^*|T \geq z). \quad (1)$$

Let z_k denote the waiting time of patient k which is set to, say, $z+1$, for patients in state 0 at z . Now $Z_k = (\min(z_k, z), I(z_k \leq z))$ is the waiting time history of patient k up to time z . Since Z_k is a vector of baseline variables at z the arguments with respect to the asymptotic properties of the pseudo-values of Jacobsen and Martinussen [2] apply in analogy.

Now $((\tilde{T}_k - z, D_k), Z_k)$, $k = 1 \dots r$, can be considered as i.i.d. replicates of the population at risk at z . Using the von Mises expansion the pseudo-value can be expressed as

$$\hat{U}_k = \theta + \psi(\tilde{T}_k - z, D_k) + o_p(1)$$

where $\theta = P(T > t^* | T \geq z) = S(t^* | T \geq z)$ denotes the survival probabilitiy at t^* of the population at risk at z ; and $\hat{S}(t^* | T \geq z)$ is an asymptotically unbiased estimate of θ .

Jacobson and Martinussen [2] showed that

$$E\left[\psi\left(\tilde{T}_k - z, D_k\right) \mid Z_k\right] = \theta_k - \theta.$$

Here, $\theta_k = P\left(T_k > t^* \mid T_k \geq z, Z_k\right) = S\left(t^* \mid T \geq z, Z_k\right)$ is the survival probability at t^* conditional on both, being alive at z and the waiting time history of patient k up to z .

Consequently it follows that

$$E\left[\hat{U}_k\right] = \theta_k + o_p(1).$$

By varying z between 0 and t^{search} , a plethora of pseudo-values could be computed. However, the primary interest is in values of z that correspond to actually observed waiting times $w_i, i = 1 \dots m$

. Given $z = w_i$ and a patient with $z_k = w_i$, then

$$\theta_k = S\left(t^* \mid T \geq w_i, W = w_i\right) = \int_{w_i}^{t^*} \lambda_{12}(v, v - w_i) dv$$

which is the quantity to be estimated in the main paper.

Section B: Waiting time distribution in patients with a donor

Here, the density $f_{01}(w)$ of partly unobservable times to donor identification (waiting times) in patients with a donor available is related to the density $q(w)$ of observable waiting times up to t^{search} not prevented by competing risks, like death and early censoring represented by $\lambda_{02}(t)$ and $\lambda_C(t)$, respectively. Now,

$$q(w) = \frac{1}{p_m} \lambda_{01}(w) \exp\left[-\int_0^w \lambda_{01}(v) + \lambda_{02}(v) + \lambda_C(v) dv\right]$$

with $p_m = \int_0^{t_{search}} \lambda_{01}(x) \exp\left[-\int_0^x \lambda_{01}(v) + \lambda_{02}(v) + \lambda_c(v) dv\right] dx$, so that $\int_0^{t_{search}} q(w) dw = 1$. Here, p_m is

the expected proportion of patients with observed $0 \rightarrow 1$ transition in the population of patients with a donor available. Due to the competing risks $\lambda_{02}(t)$ and $\lambda_c(t)$, longer waiting times are underrepresented among the m patients with observed $0 \rightarrow 1$ transitions.

For the estimation of $S_1(t^*)$, the density $f_{01}(w)$ of times to donor identification of all patients with a donor available (includes patients with ceased donor search) is needed. This quantity is

$$f_{01}(w) = \lambda_{01}(w) \exp\left[-\int_0^w \lambda_{01}(v) dv\right]$$

and it is linked to $q(w)$ by

$$f_{01}(w) = \frac{q(w) p_m}{\exp\left[-\int_0^w \lambda_{02}(v) + \lambda_c(v) dv\right]}.$$

Given $W=w$, the denominator represents the probability that a $0 \rightarrow 1$ transition can actually be observed at time w .

Section C: Generation of simulated data

Section C is concerned with the generation of simulated survival and waiting times. Parameter values used in the simulations can be found in Table S1.

Let $S_{wb}(t; \omega, \vartheta) = \exp(-\omega t^\vartheta)$ denote the survival function of a Weibull distribution for $t \geq 0$, where $\vartheta > 0$ is the shape parameter and $\omega > 0$ represents the scale parameter. Let $f_{wb}(t; \omega, \vartheta)$ denote the corresponding density distribution.

For direct $0 \rightarrow 2$ transitions, the simulations are based on the parametric mixture survival function

$$S_0(t) = \pi_{02} S_{wb}(t; \omega_{02}, \theta_{02}) + (1 - \pi_{02}).$$

Here, $(1 - \pi_{02})$ is the proportion of cured patients and $S_0(t)$ converges to $(1 - \pi_{02})$ with increasing t . This mimics the typical situation in paediatric oncology where the plateau in the survival

function indicates the presence of long-term survivors (cured patients). π_{02} is the proportion of

patients that are susceptible for a direct $0 \rightarrow 2$ transition with corresponding survival function

$S_{wb}(t; \omega_{02}, \theta_{02})$. Until $t^{search} = t^* = 5$ years, the hazard functions for a $0 \rightarrow 2$ transition are

$$\lambda_{02}(t) = \lambda'_{02}(t) = \frac{\pi_{02} f_{wb}(t; \omega_{02}, \theta_{02})}{S_0(t)}$$

in the populations with and without donor available,

respectively. More details on parametric mixture survival function can be found in Sposto [4].

Additionally, times to $0 \rightarrow 1$ transitions (waiting times w) need to be simulated. It is assumed that a

proportion of π_{01} patients have a donor available. For scenarios A-G, a log-normal waiting time

distribution $f_{01}(w)$ with parameters μ_{01} and σ_{01} , truncated at t^{search} , is used. The cumulative

density function of the log-normal distribution is for $x > 0$

$$CDF(x, \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\log(x)} e^{-\left[\frac{(v-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right]} dv$$

In scenario I, discrete waiting times at $w=0.5, 1$ and 3 years and the probability mass function

$$f_{01}(w) = 1/3 \text{ are assumed.}$$

For the population with a donor available and for a specific waiting time $w \leq t$, the following form of the hazard function for a $1 \rightarrow 2$ transition was used in the simulations:

$$\lambda_{12}(t, t-w) = r\lambda_{02}(t) + \lambda_T(t-w)$$

Here $\lambda_{12}(t, t-w)$ depends on both, the time elapsed since time zero and the time elapsed since the $0 \rightarrow 1$ transition at time w . The first term, $r\lambda_{02}(t)$, represents the long-term effect of the time-dependent intervention, which is favourable when $r < 1$. The second term, $\lambda_T(t-w)$, allows for additional short-term risks due to the intervention and follows a Weibull mixture distribution $S_T(t-w) = \pi_T S_{wb}(t-w; \omega_T, \mathcal{G}_T) + (1 - \pi_T)$. The proportion π_T represents the specific intervention related events in state 1 that would be observed in absence of any other competing events.

Section D: Software implementation

The proposed method can be straightforwardly implemented using standard routines available in the majority of statistical software packages. Firstly, Kaplan-Meier estimates are repeatedly computed to derive generalised pseudo-values; subsequently, a generalised linear model is fitted.

In SAS, the procedure LIFETEST provides Kaplan-Meier estimates for survival probabilities. The procedure GENMOD can be used for fitting a generalised linear model. Note, that the model specification is done identically to the original pseudo-value approach, e.g. see Klein et al. [5] for details.

In R, the function ‘survfit’ in the package SURVIVAL can be used for Kaplan-Meier estimates.

The generalised linear model can be estimated using the object ‘geese’ in the package GEEPACK.

For a more detailed description of the technical implementation see Klein et al. [5].

Additional file 1: Table S1: Specification of the simulated scenarios: parameter values and ‘true’ 5-year survival probabilities

Scenario		Survival times						Waiting times ¹			True survival probabilities ²		
		Transition 0→2			Transition 1→2			Transition 0→1			$S_0(5)$	$S_1(5)$	
		$1-\pi_{02}$	ω_{02}	\mathcal{G}_{02}	r	π_T	ω_T	\mathcal{G}_T	π_{01}	μ_{01}	σ_{01}		
I	Discrete	0.18	0.150	1.5	0.1	0.15	3	1.3	0.75	-	-	0.333	0.620
A	Balduzzi 2005	0.4	0.629	1.3	0.33	0.18	8.5	2.5	0.25	log(0.4)	0.3	0.404	0.562
B	Gale 1998	0.18	0.179	1.5	0.1	0.35	3	1.3	0.4	log(0.5)	0.3	0.291	0.547
C	Goldstone 2008	0.5	0.210	1.8	0.3	0.16	10	1.5	0.4	log(0.7)	0.3	0.511	0.659
D	Locaciulli 2007	0.7	0.653	1.2	0.4	0.16	4	2.5	0.4	log(0.4)	0.3	0.703	0.703
E	PH	0.18	0.179	1.5	0.75	0	-	-	0.4	log(0.5)	0.3	0.291	0.390
F	No diff.	0.5	0.210	1.8	1	0	-	-	0.4	log(0.7)	0.3	0.511	0.511
G	Late SCTs	0.18	0.150	1.5	0.1	0.15	3	1.3	0.45	log(2)	0.8	0.333	0.569

1) $t^{search}=t^*=5$ years

2) True survival probabilities $S_0(5)$ and $S_1(5)$ were calculated using computations and simulations in SAS and numerical integration in

Mathematica according to equation (3) and (2) of the main paper, respectively.

Additional file 1: Table S2: Model-based and Monte-Carlo standard-errors for simulation study 1

			wGLM ¹		WGLM ad-hoc ²	
	Donor	w	SE _{est} ³	SD _{sim} ⁴	SE _{est} ³	SD _{sim} ⁴
n=1000 ⁵	No Donor	--	0.125	0.128	0.125	0.128
	Yes	--	0.078	0.070	0.098	0.104
		0.5	0.164	0.158	0.172	0.168
		1	0.134	0.132	0.161	0.158
		3	0.106	0.083	0.191	0.177
n=400 ⁵	No Donor	--	0.210	0.216	0.210	0.216
	Yes	--	0.124	0.112	0.156	0.171
		0.5	0.263	0.253	0.277	0.269
		1	0.224	0.211	0.269	0.254
		3	0.170	0.129	0.309	0.286

- 1) The weighted generalised linear model (wGLM) uses $\hat{V}_{i,1}(t^*)$ according to equation (6)
- 2) The weighted generalised linear model (wGLM) uses the ad-hoc correction suggested to estimate $\hat{V}_{i,1}(t^*)$ (with one repetition per observation per simulation run)
- 3) Mean of standard errors of the generalised linear model (empirical ‘sandwich’ estimator)
- 4) Standard deviations of the parameter estimates of 1000 simulation runs (Monte-Carlo standard deviations)
- 5) Entire sample with and without a donor with 25 % in every subgroup: without donor and donor found at $w=0.5, 1$ and 3 , respectively

Additional file 1: Table S3: Model-based and Monte-Carlo standard-errors for simulation study 2

β_0	uniform censoring	n=1000 ³		n=400 ³	
		SE _{est} ¹	SD _{sim} ²	SE _{est} ¹	SD _{sim} ²
A	0-11	0.053	0.051	0.085	0.082
B	0-11	0.062	0.063	0.098	0.095
C	0-11	0.067	0.068	0.107	0.107
D	0-11	0.079	0.080	0.126	0.126
E	0-11	0.062	0.062	0.098	0.095
F	0-11	0.067	0.068	0.107	0.107
G	0-11	0.060	0.063	0.095	0.097
G	0-6	0.083	0.083	0.133	0.132
$\beta_0 + \beta_1$					
A	0-11	0.111	0.111	0.177	0.181
B	0-11	0.087	0.092	0.137	0.142
C	0-11	0.099	0.098	0.157	0.154
D	0-11	0.101	0.105	0.161	0.162
E	0-11	0.082	0.081	0.130	0.129
F	0-11	0.087	0.087	0.138	0.142
G	0-11	0.115	0.125	0.182	0.187
G	0-6	0.149	0.154	0.239	0.246
β_1					
A	0-11	0.123	0.122	0.196	0.196
B	0-11	0.107	0.112	0.169	0.173
C	0-11	0.119	0.118	0.190	0.184
D	0-11	0.129	0.127	0.204	0.201
E	0-11	0.103	0.101	0.163	0.161
F	0-11	0.110	0.109	0.174	0.174
G	0-11	0.131	0.132	0.208	0.204
G	0-6	0.173	0.169	0.278	0.268

- 1) Mean of standard errors of the generalised linear model (empirical ‘sandwich’ estimator)
- 2) Standard deviations of the parameter estimates of 1000 simulation runs (Monte-Carlo standard deviations)
- 3) entire sample with and without a donor

Additional file 1: Figure S1: Survival scenarios used in simulation study 2 with $t^{search}=5$ years

References

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